

Sample Case Study Prompt and Student Instructions Handout_1

CASE. Leukocyte Adhesion Deficiency (LAD)

Case Studies in Immunology. A Clinical Companion. 7e Garland Science

SUMMARY

White blood cells (leukocytes), like red blood cells (erythrocytes), travel through blood vessels to make their way around the body. However, unlike red blood cells, leukocytes must intermittently exit the blood vessel to visit lymph nodes or sites of infection via a process called leukocyte extravasation. Circulation through the lymphatic system and eventually to sites of infection or injury ensures proper pathogen clearance and wound healing. Adhesion molecules (e.g., selectins, integrins) expressed by the endothelium can interact with ligands on the surface of leukocytes to signal leukocyte entry into peripheral tissues or lymphatics. This leukocyte extravasation is a multi-step process: weak, “rolling” adhesion along endothelial cells slows leukocytes, activates cell adhesion molecules, allows them to firmly adhere to cell adhesion molecules on the vascular endothelium, resulting in diapedesis and transendothelial migration.

Genetic deficiencies that cause reduced adhesion molecule expression can result in inefficient immune responses and wound healing. In this case study, we will discuss Leukocyte Adhesion Deficiency by focusing on a patient that lacked the leukocyte integrin subunit CD18.

CASE STUDY PREPARATION INSTRUCTIONS (TO DO BEFORE CLASS)

Please complete the following sections of the module before our class meeting.

1. Read “Case. Leukocyte Adhesion Deficiency (LAD) Week 1.pdf”.
2. Review and be prepared to discuss the “Discussion Questions” listed below. NOTE: the questions below differ from those in the pdf.
3. Bring your own questions to class to be thoroughly prepared to contribute to the interactive discussion session. We will discuss the questions listed below in class and/or any student-driven questions that arise throughout the discussion session. If time allows, we may choose to discuss the questions found at the end of the case.

Remember, you will receive points for your appropriate participation during case study discussions. Participation includes providing answers to discussion questions and/or asking questions of your own!

DISCUSSION QUESTIONS

1. Which step (see Fig. 27.1) of Leukocyte migration is affected by CD18 deficiency?
 2. What happens to leukocytes as they pass through blood vessels near the site of infection? How would this change with a type I LAD? Use Figure 27.1 to outline and describe the 4 main steps of leukocyte extravasation.
 3. In patients with LAD, would you expect that the microbicidal function of leukocytes is impaired? Why or why not?
 4. Which lab results came back as 'abnormal' in the case of Luisa Ortega (the case and Figure 27.5)? How do these relate to the LAD diagnosis?
 5. Why is the homing of T cells to lymphoid tissues normal in patients with CD18 deficiency? Why do they not succumb to opportunistic infections? What protein, if missing, might cause deficient lymphoid homing? (Figure 27.2)
 6. What is the most common sign in newborn children for suspicion of LAD?
 7. Why is bone marrow transplantation an effective treatment? In the case of Luisa, what does "full chimerism" mean after her bone marrow transplant? Is the desired result?
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VIDEOS – SHOWN IN CLASS

Example footage of mouse leukocytes rolling, tightly adhering, and migrating into tissue. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LamIRIcvnB4>

The **Instructor Answers to the Discussion Questions** are available upon request. Please contact Aimee Bernard (Aimee.Bernard@cuanschutz.edu).

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